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PIJSSL

Website: www.pijssl.com

E-mail: editor.pijssl@gmail.com

Youth Political Participation and problems

Billal Ahmad Bhat

Research scholar, Dept of Political science and Public administration Vikram University Ujjain, M.P.

Email: billalbhat1@gmail.com

ABSTRACT :

India is a very “young country” it is anticipated that fifty four percent of our inhabitants is below the age of 25 and rest is trying to look that way which made them important segment, and hope of the future of our country lies upon them. However youth of character, intelligence, self sacrificing can shape the destiny of the nation. Youth devoid of energy, suffering from inertia and dullness, without bravery and mental vitality are bound to lead us nowhere. Before 1947 the value based leadership channelizes the energy and power of youth in a good way and made our country free from colonial rule. And the first Lok Sabha election were held 1952 largely the young freedom fighters jumped into the electoral contests to contribute in national building task. Since then youth participation in politics and governance has declined steadily because of certain obstacles.

INTRODUCTION :

Youth is a divergent social category. It is a period of full physical and mental development. It can be defined in a number of ways it can be viewed from the angle of process of socialization. It's essential as age category “according to oommen when we refer to youth, we have in mind an age group, usually between 15 and 30 years”. In the domain of politicians and elderly statesman , a person may be considered ‘a young’ even though he has already crossed his fiftieth year of age” according to this the term needs some clarification as gore has pointed out that youth and adulthood are not wholly age related concepts they are at least in a part social. The eruption of youth as a dynamic force today is by no means a phenomenon peculiar to our country. It is rather a universal phenomenon. The peculiar problems of present day society, particularly in a case of our country, we have made the youth much more active as compared to a few decades ago. Youth is living in the age of uncertainty, insecurity and uneasy calm. India is witnessing a demographic transition. In a country where the bridge between the celebration and mourning of diversity is wafer thin, and a time when competitions between nations and developmental targets are on an upward shift, being dynamic to the changing societal scenario and keeping in sync with the mind sets and aspirations of the citizens are of paramount importance. These aspirations are conceived by and more often reflect the wants and desires of the majority population, which according to recent findings India is the home to one of the largest and fastest growing youth population in the world. Currently it has 330 million people aged at 10-24 and if one goes by the national definition of the youth ages 13-35 then youth constitute 40% of the population. By 2020, India is slated to become the youngest nation (average age 29 years as compared to china 37, japans 48 and Europe's 49. This makes it all the more obligatory to shed light on the socio-political aspects concerning the youth. Migration of youth from rural to urban areas, education in social and civic matters, religious views, openness to constructive debates, effective leadership skills and gender sensitization are few of the many factors that contribute towards building a foundation, upon which support

systems have to be built not just to make the participation of the youth in the political sphere possible, but effective and tangible as well.

Objective

The objective of this research paper is to highlight the role of youth and obstacles of youth which hinder them in direct political participation.

Research methodology

In the present paper empirical method of data collection is used

Youth political participation

With the independence in 1947 all the dimensions of Indian youth political participation were changed and in recent past, through the advent of various platforms, both offline and online the youth of our nation has been involved in matters of public interest and have portrayed the intent to be conspicuous part of today's socio political scenario. Participation of youth in politics is as an indicator of the roles played by the young in society. No doubt, youth participation in other spheres, like family, careers, religion, are also an important part of discourse and have significant impact on all role that young people play in society and because most commentators declare that what the country needs most today is value based political leadership, especially among the youth. Indian freedom was obtained by amongst others a large cohort of young people. Thousands took on leadership roles based on the principles of patriotism and sacrificed their career and lives for the common good. Of course they rode on the guidance of adults in their own generation and the groundswell created by actions of the youth in proceeding ones.

When Jawaharlal Nehru was chosen to lead the congress party at the age of 40, in Lahore in 1929, Gandhi said: "the appointment of Jawaharlal Nehru as the captain is the proof of the trust the nation responses in its youth. Jawaharlal Nehru alone can do little. The youth of this country must be his arms and eyes. Let them prove worthy of the trust." And they did, youth participation and leadership during the Indian freedom movement is well documented

We believe that something changed in the way the elders of the freedom movement were viewing youth in those days just after independence. While putting together the founding principles, they debated on the responsibilities and duties of each segment of society. Sometimes then, acting on a reductionist and exclusivist point of view, the elders decided to approach youth in a very less manner and that is why what we get. The adults decided to shoulder a large part of the government load onto them and asked the youth to go back into the classrooms in preparation of adulthood, they were urged to reduce their roles back to their studies, careers, and families which results in our parliament is called world's oldest parliament because of increasing average age of parliamentarians with the time.

In the first two Lok Sabha average ages of MPs were 45.8. Largely it was the freedom fighters that jumped into the electoral contests in new India, hoping to contribute to the nation-building task as significantly as they had to ousting the empire. After independence too as evinced in the number of young parliamentarians in the first two Lok Sabha's youth led from the front. Since then youth participation in politics and governance has declined steadily. In the 16th lok sabha election, average age of member of parliamentarians increases to 53.86 which were 45.8 in first two Lok Sabhas this increasing average age of parliamentarians is a big cause of concern. During the last eight Lok Sabhas (1989-2014) the share of young members has not crossed one-fifth of the total strength of the Lok Sabha and the present parliament after the 2014 Lok Sabha elections was known as world oldest parliament because of the low percentage of youth between the age 25 to 40, because of the certain system in existence and other factors marsh down the youth in their political participation.

Obstacles to youth participation

Moreover there are certain obstacles which hinder the youth to participate in politics either political participation, youth is limited to electoral processes such as voting, filing petitions, staging protests and so on. The participation of youth in elections and the participation in the parliament are limited and there are many factors that marsh down the youth and hinder their participation

Perception : The perception of a common man is that politics is only for the wealthy, powerful, old and well connected/endowed, which curb them from even trying, let alone winning.

Lack of constitutional provisions : In order to be a Member of Parliament in Lok Sabha the minimum eligibility is 25 years and 30 years for the Rajya Sabha. This is one of the main reasons for the low representation of members in Parliament. People below 35 years are rarely found in political leadership positions.

Culture : The Indian culture as adopted by parents, mentors and a major part of the society is one that believes in the idea "experience comes with age" and axiomatically "the aged are always experienced". The youth, with proper systems in place, can acquire the experiences that would make them "experienced as the

aged". Society still continues to view a non-youth candidate in a more acceptable light than a young candidate in electoral situations.

While the reasons for the non-participation might be any of the following, certain systems in existence also hinder the participation of the youth in politics.

1. Non-encouragement by parents and educational institutions
2. Lack of institutionalization in the system of selection of candidates for elections
3. Corruption
4. Peer pressure
5. Unavailability of visible rewards

CONCLUSION :

The participation of the youth in elections, signing petitions, joining hands in civil protests and fasts across the country have increased. The movement that asked for the introduction of Jan Lok Pal bill gained its strength and energy only by the participation of youth in huge numbers. This clearly demonstrated that the Indian youth do engage themselves in programs and movements of National Public interest. But the decreasing share of youth in parliament since 1952 made them away in nations decision making process which needs to think broadly, and it become need of the time that there should be a proper use of government policies and programmes which are meant for to develop youth leadership, so that youth resource can be channelize in nations decision makings. Further there should be a retirement age for parliamentarians, so that proper space can avail to them and it can become possible to achieve the 2020 goal which was put forth by Abdul Kalam.

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